

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 80

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 80

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 80:0 For the choir director; <i>set to</i> [†]El Shoshannim; [°]Eduth. A Psalm of Asaph.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 80:1</p> <p>לְמִנְצַח אֶל-שְׁשִׁינִים</p>
<p>Psa. 80:1 Oh, give ear, "Shepherd of Israel, You who lead ^bJoseph like a flock; You who ^care enthroned <i>above</i> the cherubim, shine forth!</p>	<p>עֲדוּת לְאַסָּף מִזְמוֹר : 2 רְעֵה יִשְׂרָאֵל אֵל אֱלֹהֵינוּ נְהַג כְּצֹאן יוֹסֵף יֹשֵׁב הַכְּרוּבִים</p>
<p>² Before "Ephraim and Benjamin and Manasseh, ^bstir up Your power And come to save us!</p>	<p>הוֹפִיעָה : 3 לְפָנַי אֶפְרַיִם וּבְנֵימָן וּמְנַשֶּׁה עוֹרְרָה אֶת-</p>
<p>³ O God, ^arestore us And ^bcause Your face to shine <i>upon</i> us, ¹and we will be saved.</p>	<p>גְּבוּרָתְךָ וּלְכָה לִישַׁעְתָּה לָנוּ : 4 אֱלֹהִים הַשִּׁיבֵנוּ וְהָאֵר פָּנֶיךָ וְנִשְׁעָה : 5 יְהוָה</p>
<p>Psa. 80:4 O "LORD God <i>of</i> hosts, ^bHow long will You ¹be angry with the prayer of Your people?</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים צְבָאוֹת עַד-מָתַי עֲשֵׂת בְּתַכְלֵת עֲמֶךָ : 6</p>
<p>⁵ You have fed them with the "bread of tears, And You have made them to drink tears in ¹large measure.</p>	<p>הֵאֱכַלְתֶּם לֶחֶם דִּמְעָה וְתִשְׁקְמוּ בְדִמְעוֹת שְׁלִישׁ : 7</p>
<p>⁶ You make us ¹an object of contention "to our neighbors, And our enemies laugh among themselves.</p>	<p>תְּשִׁימֵנוּ מִדּוֹן לְשֹׁכְנֵינוּ וְאֵיבֵינוּ יִלְעָגוּ-לָמוּ : 8</p>
<p>⁷ O God <i>of</i> hosts, restore us And cause Your face to shine <i>upon</i> us, ¹and we will be saved.</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים צְבָאוֹת הַשִּׁיבֵנוּ וְהָאֵר פָּנֶיךָ וְנִשְׁעָה : 9 גִּפְן</p>
<p>Psa. 80:8 You removed a "vine from Egypt; You ^bdrove out the ¹nations and ^cplanted it.</p>	<p>מִמִּצְרַיִם תִּסְיַע תְּגַרֵּשׁ גּוֹזִים וּתְטַעֶה : 10 פְּנִיתָ לְפָנֶיהָ</p>
<p>⁹ You ^acleared <i>the ground</i> before it,</p>	<p>וּתְשַׁרֵּשׁ שָׂרְשֶׁיהָ וּתְמַלֵּא-</p>

And it ^btook deep root and filled the land.

¹⁰ The mountains were covered with its shadow,

And ¹the cedars of God with its ^aboughs.

¹¹ It was sending out its branches ^ato the sea

And its shoots to the River.

¹² Why have You ^abroken down its ¹hedges,

So that all who pass *that* way pick its *fruit*?

¹³ A boar from the forest ^aeats it away
And whatever moves in the field feeds on it.

Psa. 80:14 O God *of* hosts, ^aturn again now, we beseech You;

^bLook down from heaven and see, and take care of this vine,

¹⁵ Even the ^{1a}shoot which Your right hand has planted,

And on the ²son whom You have ³strengthened for Yourself.

¹⁶ It is ^aburned with fire, it is cut down;

They perish at the ^brebuke of Your countenance.

¹⁷ Let ^aYour hand be upon the man of Your right hand,

Upon the son of man whom You ^bmade strong for Yourself.

¹⁸ Then we shall not ^aturn back from You;

^bRevive us, and we will call upon Your name.

¹⁹ O LORD God of hosts, ^arestore us;

Cause Your face to shine *upon us*,
¹and we will be saved.

אֶרֶץ : כָּסּוּ הַרִים צִלָּהּ ¹¹

וְעִנְפֶיהָ אֶרְזֵי-אֵל : תְּשִׁלַּח ¹²

קִצְיֹתָהּ עֲדָיִם וְאֵל-נְהַר

יִזְנְקוּתֶיהָ : לָמָּה פָּרַצְתָּ ¹³

גְּדֵרֶיהָ וְאֲרוּתָהּ כָּל-עֲבָרֵי

דְּרָךְ : יְכַרְסֵמֶנָּה תְּחִיר ¹⁴

מִיַּעַר וְזִיז שְׁרָי יִרְעֶנָּה : ¹⁵

אֱלֹהִים צְבָאוֹת שׁוֹב-נֶאֱ

תְּבַט מִשָּׁמַיִם וּרְאֵה וּפְקֹד

גִּבְעֹן זֹאת : וְכֹנֵה אֲשֶׁר-

נִטְעָה יְמִינְךָ וְעַל-יָיִן

אֲמַצְתָּה לָךְ : שְׂרַפְתָּ בְּאֵשׁ

כְּסוּתָהּ מִגְּעֵרַת פְּנִיךָ

יֶאֱבְדוּ : תִּתֵּי-יָדְךָ עַל-

אִישׁ יְמִינְךָ עַל-בֶּן-אֲדָמָה

אֲמַצְתָּ לָךְ : וְלֹא-נִסּוּג ¹⁹

מִמֶּךָ תִּתִּינֵנוּ וּבִשְׁמֶךָ נִקְרָא :

יְהוָה אֱלֹהִים צְבָאוֹת ²⁰

הַשִּׁיבֵנוּ הָאֵל פְּנִיךָ וְנִשְׁעָה :

References

Psalm 80:1

[†]Possibly, *to the Lilies*

[°]Lit *A testimony*

Psalm 80:0

^aPs 23:1

^bPs 77:15; 78:67; Amos 5:15

^cEx 25:22; 1 Sam 4:4; 2 Sam 6:2; Ps 99:1

Psalm 80:2

^aNum 2:18-24

^bPs 35:23

Psalm 80:3

¹Or *that we may*

^aPs 60:1; 80:7, 19; 85:4; 126:1; Lam 5:21

^bNum 6:25; Ps 4:6; 31:16

Psalm 80:4

¹Lit *smoke against*

^aPs 59:5; 84:8

^bPs 79:5; 85:5

Psalm 80:5

¹Lit *a third part of a*

^aPs 42:3; 102:9; Is 30:20

Psalm 80:6

¹Lit *a strife to*

^aPs 44:13; 79:4

Psalm 80:7

¹Or *that we may*

Psalm 80:8

¹Or *Gentiles*

^aPs 80:15; Is 5:1, 2, 7; Jer 2:21; 12:10; Ezek 17:6; 19:10

^bJosh 13:6; 2 Chr 20:7; Ps 44:2; Acts 7:45

^cJer 11:17; 32:41; Ezek 17:23; Amos 9:15

Psalm 80:9

^aEx 23:28; Josh 24:12; Is 5:2

^bHos 14:5

Psalm 80:10

¹Or *its boughs are like the cedars of God*

^aGen 49:22

Psalm 80:11

^aPs 72:8

Psalm 80:12

¹Or *walls, fences*

^aPs 89:40; Is 5:5

Psalm 80:13

^aJer 5:6

Psalm 80:14

^aPs 90:13

^bPs 102:19; Is 63:15

Psalm 80:15

¹Or *root*

²Or figuratively: *branch*

³Or *secured*

^aPs 80:8

Psalm 80:16

^a2 Chr 36:19; Ps 74:8; Jer 52:13

^bPs 39:11; 76:6

Psalm 80:17

^aPs 89:21

^bPs 80:15

Psalm 80:18

^aIs 50:5

^bPs 71:20

Psalm 80:19

¹Or *that we may*

^aPs 80:3

Targum

Psa. 80:1 For praise; concerning those who sit in the Sanhedrin who occupy themselves with the testimony of the Torah; composed by Asaph; a psalm. ² Caretaker of Israel, hear; you who guide the coffin of Joseph like a flock; you whose presence abides between the cherubim, shine forth. ³ Before Ephraim and Benjamin and Manasseh, stir up your mighty power for us; and it is right for you to redeem us. ⁴ O God, bring us back from our exile, and shine the splendor of your countenance upon us, and we will be redeemed. ⁵ O LORD God Sabaoth, how long have you not accepted the prayer of your people! ⁶ You fed them bread soaked in tears, and you made them drink the wine of tears in triple measure. ⁷ You made us a source of contention for our neighbors, and our enemies will jeer at them. ⁸ God Sabaoth, bring us back from our exile, and shine the splendor of your countenance upon us, and we will be redeemed. ⁹ The house of Israel, which is likened to a vine, you brought out of Egypt; you chased away the Gentiles from the land of Israel and planted them. ¹⁰ You cleared out the Canaanites before them, and you uprooted their roots and filled the land. ¹¹ The mountains of Jerusalem cover the shadow of the temple, and the academies, say the scholars, are strong, which are likened to mighty cedars. ¹² You made branches grow, you sent out her pupils to the Great Sea, and her children to the river Euphrates. ¹³ Why have you attacked her walls? and [now] all those who pass on the way are pruning her. ¹⁴ The boar from the forest will root her up, and the wild cock will be sustained by her. ¹⁵ God Sabaoth, turn now, look from heaven, and see, and remember this vine in mercy. ¹⁶ And the branch that your right hand planted, and the King Messiah whom you made mighty for yourself. ¹⁷ [It is] being burned by fire and crushed; they will perish because of the rebuke that [comes] from your presence. ¹⁸ Let your hand be on the man to whom you have sworn with your right hand, on the son of man whom you made mighty for yourself. ¹⁹ We will not turn away from the fear of you; you will sustain us and we will call on your name. ²⁰ O LORD God Sabaoth, bring us back from exile; shine the splendor of your countenance upon us and we will be redeemed.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was dedicated to the generations of Israelites who lived in Exile in Babylon. From the establishment of the nation of Israel, the people prepared for attacks from the nations surrounding them. The Ten Tribes that constituted the northern kingdom disappeared after the Assyrian invasion. In the Babylonian Exile, the people taken were kept together in Susa and Babylon. This foreign land did become home to future generations. The children born in Babylonia and Susa only knew about the Promised Land and the LORD's Temple through the stories that were passed down by the family and community.

Superscript

The superscript is addressed to the Sefirah Netzach. It is also for roses as a testimony. The rose was a metaphor for Israel. She was weak like rose petals, but Israel's thorns were from the LORD. Thorns protect roses from being destroyed by animals. The thorns are a metaphor for the LORD's protection.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, for roses; as a testimony, a psalm of Asaf.

Verse one

In this verse, the name Joseph means all the tribes from Jacob. The Psalmist indicates what Joseph's role was in Israel's history. When Joseph was first taken to Egypt, he was tempted to abandon his love for the LORD. He could have engaged in activities that were against the LORD's law. Instead, Joseph demonstrated his beliefs and

convictions. Using foresight, it was Joseph being sold into slavery, and the Midianites then sold him to Egypt, which allowed Jacob's family to survive a seven-year famine. Joseph can be viewed as a savior for the people. Therefore, Jews should try to emulate Joseph. They need to stay close to the LORD by following the Laws of the Torah and the words of the Prophets; in other words, they should emulate Joseph. The Psalmist asks for the Light of the LORD to shine upon Israel, thus removing the dark age that the nation was in.

**O Shepherd of Israel, incline Your ear! You Who lead Joseph like a flock,
O You Who are enthroned upon the Cheribum, shine forth.**

Verses four through seven

These verses constitute a cry for help for the people in Babylon's Exile. The people prayed that the Sefirah Gevurah would intervene and bring justice. The people, in general, felt that their exile punishment was too severe for the violations of the Torah committed by the people.

**O God, God of Hosts, until when, have You fixed the afterglow of Your
wrath to the prayers of Your people?**

**You have fed them with the bread of tears; You have made them drain
their measured drink with tears.**

**You make us the target of strife for our neighbors; and our enemies mock
as they please.**

**O God of Hosts, lead us back and cause Your countenance to shine so
that we shall be saved.**

Verses eight through eleven

The usage of the “vine” is an allegory for Israel. Ezekiel portrays Israel as a vine. He explained that the vine was the noblest among all plants because of its fruit. A midrash about Adam and Eve says that the LORD allowed them to take one thing from the Garden of Eden. That item was a vine. Therefore, wine became a sacred drink. The first plant planted by Noah was the vine from the Garden of Eden. In this Psalm the vine is a metaphor for Israel.

“Mountains were covered by its shadow” refers to the branches of the trees that held the fruit harvest.

Israel occupied a central position in the world’s trade lanes. The two main trade routes went through Israel. The city of Meggido was at the crossroads of the trading lanes. Therefore, this city was fought over for centuries. The nation that controlled this city had control of taxing the traders who traveled through it.

You carry a vine out of Egypt; You drive out nations and plant it.

You cleared a place before it; it took root and filled the land.

Mountains were covered with its shadow, and their branches became cedars of God.

It stretches its fruit – its branches to the sea and its sucking shoots toward the river.

Verses fifteen and sixteen

Israel is the Son of God because the first group of men to recognize the LORD as “Father” was Israel. Israel was also known as the intelligent collaborator in the LORD’s work of salvation for all humanity.

The foundation which Your right hand has laid, the son whom You have made strong for Yourself.

Burned by fire, cut down, they perished utterly before the threat of Your countenance.

Verse seventeen

“The might of your spirit” this a common expression used for the spirit of the LORD that descends upon a prophet. It is common in Ezekiel (1:3, 3:21, 37:1, 40:1).

May the might of Your spirit come upon the man of Your right hand, upon the son of mankind whom You have made strong for Yourself.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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